

A Novel Benchmarking Approach to Assess Fire Safety of Liquid Electrolytes in Lithium-Ion Batteries

*Mingyang Zhang, Junchen Xiao, Wei Tang, Yi He, Peng Tan, Maciej Haranczyk, and De-Yi Wang**

M. Zhang, J. Xiao, W. Tang, Dr. M. Haranczyk, Prof. D.-Y. Wang

IMDEA Materials Institute

C/Eric Kandel, 2, Getafe, Madrid 28906, Spain.

E-mail: deyi.wang@imdea.org

M. Zhang, J. Xiao

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

E.T.S. de Ingenieros de Caminos, Madrid 28040, Spain.

W. Tang

Materials Science and Engineering Area, Escuela Superior de Ciencias Experimentales y Tecnología

Universidad Rey Juan Carlos

Calle Tulipán s/n, 28933 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain

Dr. Y. He, Prof. P. Tan

Department of Thermal Science and Energy Engineering

University of Science and Technology of China (USTC), Hefei, Anhui 230026, China

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Abstract: Establishing authoritative electrolyte safety assessment methods at laboratory levels is crucial for addressing conflicts from thermal runaway of lithium-ion batteries. However, self-extinguishing time (SET), as the most widely used evaluation method now, lacks benchmarks and heavily relies on the specific implementation of test procedures. This work systematically summarizes and investigates key test parameters. Based on repeatability and reliability, burning a glassfiber separator ($\Phi 16$ mm) with absorption of 0.1 g liquid electrolyte (LE) can be proposed as a unified method. The concept of self-extinguishing efficiency (SEE) is further proposed with a new evaluation criterion of (i) $SEE \leq 70$, Flammable; (ii) $70 < SEE < 90$, Flame Retarded; (iii) $90 \leq SEE \leq 100$, Nonflammable. The feasibility of the new protocol is verified by employment in evaluating the effects of 15 representative flame retardants (FRs) on combustion behaviors of LEs. Meanwhile, the underlying flame retardancy mechanism is revealed, indicating that preceding or simultaneous vaporization and pyrolysis of FRs in conjunction with the decomposition of LE promote mitigating electrolyte fire risk. In addition, machine learning is employed to aid in analyzing the significance of various features on SEE, providing further validation of the proposed mechanism. This work provides a benchmark for the safety evaluation of LEs, facilitating the advancement of fire-safe batteries.

1. Introduction

Under the advocacy of transforming energy structure and developing various alternative energy resources, such as wind, tidal, geothermal, and solar energy, it is of vital importance to eliminate the accompanied intermittent by integrating with energy grids. Compared to other secondary batteries, owing to its lower memory effect, better cycle stability, higher energy density, faster charging rate, and lower self-discharge rate, lithium-ion battery (LIB) has been viewed as a competent candidate for phasing out fossil fuels and has dominated electric vehicles, large energy storage stations, and other power fields in recent decades. Despite the satisfying electrochemical performances that LIBs offer, the intrinsic safety issue remains challenging for its wider applications in various scenarios.^[1] Targeted to this, researchers have poured significant efforts into improving the safety of batteries both from materials development and battery management systems (BMS) sides.^[2] Nevertheless, the importance of establishing authoritative and reliable evaluations for battery safety has been grossly underestimated.

So far, several standards have been proposed one after another to regulate the safety assessment of LIBs, for example, IEC 62660-3 (International, 2022), ISO 6469-1 (International, 2019), and GB/T 36276 (China, 2018) correspond to the cell, the pack and the module, and the system level, respectively.^[3] However, the above existing evaluation methods are mainly focused on industrial levels and are difficult to implement on laboratory scales. Furthermore, although many works have emphasized their improvement of fire safety with some indicators, the absence of benchmarks leads to the occurrence of multitudinous methods without comparability, and this challenge presents a more formidable situation when considering liquid electrolyte (LE).

As the blood enables continuous ion conduction in LIBs, electrolyte plays an important role in overall performance, including energy density, cycle stability, and safety. To achieve both high dielectric constant and low viscosity, current commercial electrolytes employ a combination of lithium salts and solvents composed of cyclic carbonates (e.g., ethylene carbonate (EC) and propylene carbonate (PC)) alongside linear carbonates (e.g., ethyl methyl carbonate (EMC), diethyl carbonate (DEC), and dimethyl carbonate (DMC)).^[4] While these formulations deliver exceptional electrochemical performance, the volatile and flammable nature of organic solvents poses a huge challenge to the fire safety of the whole battery system. As presented in Table S1, when linear carbonates exhibit low viscosities that can enhance molecular freedom, their low flash points pose stability concerns, particularly when exposed to the air or in the presence of Li salt.^[5]

The first work regarding flammability evaluation of LE was conducted by Wang et al.,^[6] where glassy filters were adopted to immerse LE, and the samples were ignited vertically on an iron stand to record the burning time regarding the test procedure of plastic materials. After that, Xu et al. proposed a concept of “self-extinguishing time (SET)” in 2002, which is defined by normalizing the burning time against the mass of LE as Equation 1 shows:^[7]

$$\text{SET} = \frac{\text{Burning time}}{\text{Mass of LE}} \quad (1)$$

where burning time and mass of LE correspond to the time from ignition to extinguishment and the mass of LE tested. Meanwhile, three different categories have been classified as follows: (i) nonflammable: $\text{SET} \leq 6 \text{ S g}^{-1}$; (ii) flame retarded: $6 < \text{SET} < 20 \text{ S g}^{-1}$; (iii) flammable: $\text{SET} \geq 20 \text{ S g}^{-1}$. In addition to SET, similar descriptive features were also put forward, including propagation rate and relative rate of SET, as illustrated by Equation 2 and 3, respectively:

$$\text{Propagation rate} = \frac{\text{Damaged length}}{\text{Propagation time}} \quad (2)$$

where a glassfiber wick with $\sim 140 \text{ mm}$ length, absorbing $\sim 5 \text{ g}$ of LE samples, is set horizontally and ignited to allow flame to spread for $\sim 100 \text{ mm}$ to record the propagation time.^[8]

$$\text{Relative rate} = \frac{\text{SET}_0 - \text{SET}}{\text{SET}_0} \quad (3)$$

where SET_0 is obtained from the LE sample without additives, and SET is the value of modified LE.^[9] Among these methods, SET has been widely recognized and extensively applied as an indispensable descriptor for LE safety. Subsequently, not only for LE, SET has also been adopted to evaluate the combustion behaviors of separators and gel polymer electrolytes.^[10]

Unlike polymeric materials, the combustion process of liquid samples exhibits inherent distinctions, characterized by the simultaneous occurrence of intricate physicochemical processes, including volatilization, vaporization, and pyrolysis.^[11] Hence, the distinctive structural and dimensional characteristics of matrixes employed for absorbing electrolytes in tests significantly impact combustion behaviors of LEs, which ultimately affects the comparability of final results. The lack of a unified description towards SET hinders the effective safety evaluation of LEs and impedes the progress of LIB technology. Therefore, establishing a systematic and normalized electrolyte safety assessment system is crucial. While previous studies have acknowledged this challenge, to the best of our knowledge, the development of benchmarks for SET method has not been explored yet.^[12]

In this work, we present a comprehensive introduction and summary of the conventional SET criterion, underscoring the significance of establishing normalized protocols for its measurement and evaluation. To achieve comparability across various studies, we propose a concept of “self-extinguishing efficiency (SEE)”, and systematically compare several typical

testing methods (both placed and adsorbed methods). In pursuit of repeatability, reliability, low cost, and ease of operation as the reference, two methods are screened: loaded with battery cases and absorbed by separators. Subsequently, 15 commercial flame retardants (FRs) are applied to the electrolyte to assess the desirability of the above two methods. Eventually, the unified method of horizontally burning glassfiber separators with a diameter of 16 mm and absorbing 0.1 g of electrolyte is established. Thermocouple detection, FTIR-TGA, SEM, and temperature field simulation are conducted to investigate the difference in flame retardant effectiveness among additives, and the mechanism of FRs in liquid electrolytes is proposed. Furthermore, machine learning (ML) is used to assist in the analysis of different models to further verify the mechanism. This study makes a significant contribution to the field of fire safety evaluation for electrolytes and provides valuable guidance for the design of innovative fire-safe electrolyte systems.

2. Results and discussion

In the plastic materials field, Standard 94 of the Underwriters Laboratories (UL94) is accepted worldwide as a predominant standard for the categorization of flame retardancy and an indication of plastic acceptability by considering the burning time, droplet formation, and the duration of afterglow time.^[13] Based on this, the modified method, SET, has been created to value the flammability of LEs by immobilizing them in porous carrier materials, such as glassfiber and cotton. Instead of burning time that is dramatically impacted by the sample amount, SET, a normalized value, is thought to reflect the burnability of LEs quantitatively.

Depending on the format of sample handling, SET can generally be divided into two categories: absorbed and placed (**Figure 1a**). However, due to the lack of united instruction on test details, various types and sizes of adsorbent materials and carrying containers, as well as a wide range of sample mass/volume have been applied in different studies. To reveal the embarrassment of the current situation, we have listed the testing details of 15 representative works published in the last two decades (2002-2023) in Table 1. Plenty of porous carrier materials such as glassfiber, cotton, separators, and wicks have been used to soak up LE samples since their superb wettability towards liquids can reduce evaporation during the test. However, the effects of discrepancy in density and size on their wettability and loading capabilities have been neglected. A large amount of work is performed with loadings (usually less than 0.5 g) much below their saturation capacity, which can arouse problems with uneven liquid distribution. Meanwhile, volume (100-500 μL) has been used as the quantitative parameter rather than mass to determine the loading amount, which may cause deviations during

calculation. For example, in two works using SET to evaluate the same electrolyte of 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DEC=1/1 (w/w), it is astonishing that two works reported SET values of 63.5 and 140 S g⁻¹ respectively,^[14] implying the essentiality of establishing a benchmark for the LE safety assessment system.

Table 1. State-of-art experimental details in SET tests.

Ref	Absorb or Place	Materials or Containers	Flammable	Shape (mm)	LE amount	LE composition	SET ₀	Comments
[7]	Absorb	Linear-shaped wick	Y	Φ ^{a)} : 3-5	0.05-0.1 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 1/1 (w/w)	~60	The first proposed work
[15]	Absorb	Cotton swab wick	Y	Φ: 10	100 μL	1.2 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 3/7 (v/v)	23 (in S)	Placed in a fume hood with an airflow (90 ft/S)
[16]	Absorb	Glassfiber wick ball	N	Φ: 3-5	0.1-0.2 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in DMC/EC/EMC: 1/1/1 (v/v/v)	106	Placed on an “O” shaped iron shelf
[17]	Absorb	Glassfiber ball	N	Φ: 10	0.5 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 1/3 (v/v)	49	-
[14a]	Absorb	Glassfiber separator	N	Φ: 20	500 μL	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC: 1/1 (w/w)	63.5	A custom-built device with a UV light detector
[18]	Absorb	Glassfiber separator	N	Φ: 12 t ^{b)} : 0.67	400 μL	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 3/7 (v/v)	~70	4 layers of Glassfiber discs suspended on a needle, use stormproof lighters from 3.5 cm height, ignited for 10 S
[19]	Absorb	Glassfiber wick	N	Φ: 8 l ^{c)} : 40	1 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in DMC/EC/EMC: 1/1/1 (w/w/w)	60 (in S)	Placed horizontally on a stand
[20]	Absorb	Glassfiber sheet	N	w ^{d)} : 10 l: 100	4 mL	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in DMC/EC/PC: 1/1/1 (v/v/v)	47.104/ 47.037/ 46.638	Samples were placed vertically, Bunsen burner ignited below samples 1.0 cm with a different ignition time of 2/3/4 ±0.05 S
[21]	Absorb	Glassfiber sheet	N	w: 20 l: 50	~5 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 3/7 (v/v)	~22	Samples hung on an iron shelf
[22]	Place	Watch glass	N	Φ: 70	0.5 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 3/7 (w/w)	59±2	Ignited with a barbecue gas burner for 3 S (at most 20 S)
[23]	Place	Battery case	N	Φ: 20	0.5 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC: 3/7 (v/v)	70 (in S)	-
[14b]	Absorb	Cotton ball	Y	0.5 g	0.2 g	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DEC: 1/1 (w/w)	140	-
[24]	Place	Watch glass	N	-	3 g	1.15 M LiPF ₆ in EC/EMC: 3/7 (-)	40	-
[25]	Place	Battery case	N	Φ: 20	500 μL	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC: 1/1 (v/v)	83.6	Use candles as the igniter
[26]	Absorb	Glassfiber strip	N	-	-	1.0 M LiPF ₆ in EC/DMC: 1/1 (v/v)	17	-

a): diameter; b): thickness; c): length; d): width

Besides utilizing adsorbent matrixes, researchers also take direct burning of LEs as an alternative. Since the combustion of electrolytes occurs in both liquid and gas phases, the exposed area and heat dissipation ability of vessels have a strong influence on the vapor emission rate. The key to this approach is choosing a suitable container with specific shapes and properties, and the common ones now are glass watch (GW) and battery case (BC).

Figure 1. (a) Enumeration and classification of SET test experimental details, (b) distribution of SET₀ values for four types of LEs (where EC/DEC group include EC/DEC (1:1, v/v), EC/DEC (1:2, v/v), and EC/DEC (1:1, w/w); EC/DMC group include EC/DMC (1:1, v/v), EC/DMC (2:1, v/v), EC/DMC (3:7, v/v), and EC/DMC (1:1, w/w); EC/EMC group include EC/EMC (1:3, v/v), EC/EMC (1:3, w/w), EC/EMC (1:1, v/v), EC/EMC (1:1, w/w), EC/EMC (3:7, v/v), and EC/EMC (3:7, w/w); TS group include EC/DMC/VC (0.475:0.475:0.5, v/v), EC/DMC/DEC (1:1:1, v/v), EC/DMC/EA (1:1:1, w/w), EC/DMC/PC (1:1:1, v/v), EC/DMC/EMC (1:1:1, v/v), and EC/DEC/EMC (1:1:1, v/v). Hollow icons represent the average value of groups. (c) Box plot for SEE classification criteria. Data were collected from previous works.^[7, 14-23] (d) Feature importance of SEE(number)-Ref and SET(number)-Ref models.

Current commercial LEs consist of lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆) salt and carbonates, which are categorized based on the composition of solvents, including EC/DMC (e.g., LP30), EC/DEC (e.g., LP40), EC/EMC (e.g., LP50), and ternary (e.g., LP71). The diversity of components causes different thermal stability properties.^[27] In Figure 1b, 48 SET₀ values are collected and depicted on a scatter plot, four groups contain 13, 16, 9, and 10 data respectively.

It is clear that each type of LE has a broad distribution, and the EC/DEC group has the largest range of 231 S g^{-1} . Meantime, the thermal stability of different electrolytes shows a dependence on the linear carbonate composition. According to the classification created by Xu et al., values greater than 20 S g^{-1} can be grouped as flammable, which is probably the basis that supports their establishment of classification. Nevertheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that the determination of SET is contingent upon the specific testing methodology employed, highlighting the unreasonable nature of the existing classification criteria. Noteworthy, the above discussion is only for unmodified groups (SET_0), the incomparability also exists or is even amplified in the modified LE system.

To surmount the challenge posed by the incomparability among various studies, the incorporation of relative rates stands out as a viable solution. Based on this, we propose a novel concept of “self-extinguishing efficiency (SEE)”.

$$SEE = 1 - \frac{SET}{SET_0} \quad (4)$$

By using this formula, we convert the SET values collected from literature into SEE and classify them into three groups according to the SET classification, each group consists of 31, 26, and 151 data respectively. These data are summarized from over 50 papers and cover 32 representative FRs, which can be structurally categorized into three types: aliphatic-based phosphate/phosphite, aromatic-based phosphate/phosphite, and cyclophosphazene-based additives as displayed in Figure S1-S3. As shown in Figure 1c, the “N, Nonflammable” group ($\text{SET} \leq 6$) manifests a prevailing distribution surpassing 90%, whereas the “R, Flame Retarded” group ($6 < \text{SET} < 20$) is predominantly situated within the 70-90% range, with the minimum score, lower quartile (Q1), median, upper quartile (Q3), and maximum score of 70%, 75%, 82%, 84%, and 95%, respectively. In contrast, the majority of the “F, Flammable” group ($\text{SET} \geq 20$) exhibits a distribution below the 70% threshold with a median value of 32%, only 8 points within 151 data discrete outside the range. As shown in Table 2, the new SEE evaluation criteria for assessment were put forward based on the above analysis. For data that belong to “Flammable” group according to the SET classification ($\text{SET} \geq 20$) but are classified into “Flame Retarded” group following the SEE classification ($90 > \text{SEE} > 70$), it is more reasonable to classify a SET value $\sim 20 \text{ S g}^{-1}$ as “Flame Retarded” if it decreases from a highly flammable SET_0 value $\sim 200 \text{ S g}^{-1}$, which is likely caused by the testing method.

The built-in function of the applied random forest (RF) algorithm to calculate the importance of features, represented by an impurity-based value quantifying the impact of a feature, serves as a powerful tool for selecting features and analyzing the influence factors. The data collected

from literature contribute to the construction of two models: SET(number)-Ref and SEE(number)-Ref models. In testsets, the R2 scores of SET(number)-Ref and SEE(number)-Ref models with the best splitting are 0.83 and 0.84, respectively, implying good prediction accuracy. In both models, the prediction errors in trainsets are from 3 to 5, and around 10 in testsets. These errors are small compared to the distribution range of collected SET and SEE values. Figure 1d presents the feature importance of regression models predicting numerical SEE and SET. The total importance of all features is 1, where higher importance indicates a greater impact of the feature on SEE or SET. In both models, the most significant feature affecting the target properties is “Mass”, followed by the features “SET0” and “FR(%)”. In detail, the concentration of FR has a more pronounced effect on SEE (0.514) compared to SET (0.383). Moreover, “SET0” exhibits greater importance in predicting SET, suggesting that SET is more sensitive to the properties of control electrolytes and testing procedures. In contrast, SEE is greatly affected by the inherent characteristics of FRs, offering a means to effectively assess additive efficacy and mitigate the influence of testing methodologies.

Table 2. SEE-based flammability evaluation criteria for LEs.

SEE (%)	Level	Denotation
$SEE \leq 70$	F	Flammable
$70 < SEE < 90$	R	Flame Retarded
$90 \leq SEE \leq 100$	N	Nonflammable

Though SEE has been created to solve the wide distribution of SET, it cannot avoid the inherent reliance on test methods. Whether SET/SEE can be used as a convincing assessment method is rooted in whether it can reflect the intrinsic flammability of LEs. Furthermore, the existence of a linear correlation between SET and electrolyte mass requires to be carefully investigated. In this regard, we conduct parallel experiments in an attempt to establish a repeatable and reliable normalized method. First of all, we chose two nonflammable materials (IP, GFS) and one flammable matrix (CW) to reveal the influence of absorbing matrix on SET. Insulfrax paper (IP) is used due to its high-temperature stability (up to 1200 °C), excellent flexibility, and strong liquid adsorption capacity. Four sizes of IP (10×10, 10×20, 20×20, and 30×30 mm) are prepared to achieve a wide range of adsorption levels. As shown in **Figure 2a** and Figure S4, a higher saturation amount (up to 3.6 g) can be obtained with the increase in size. For the same size, the burning time prolongs with the loading amount increasing, accompanying a gradual decrease of SET values. Currently, cotton wick (CW) is widely adopted to absorb LE to conduct the fire safety test. In Figure S5a, the saturation amount increases with the length and diameter of the wick, along with the burning time extending and

the SET decreasing. Moreover, as the sample mass increases, the spread of data becomes more concentrated. Apart from wick, separator is another superior adsorbent material owing to its outstanding wetting capability and effective liquid retention. Commercial LIB separators predominantly consist of polyolefin-based materials, such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), or their composite materials. Although they have commendable electrochemical stability, they lack heat resistance and struggle to absorb and retain electrolytes, making them unsuitable for combustion experiments.^[28] In contrast, glassfiber separators (GFS, Whatman) are used for the burning test in this study due to their excellent solvent resistance and splendid thermal resistance. Five specifications of discs (Φ 10, 12.6, 16, 26, and 37 mm) are punched, with saturated masses of 0.04, 0.06, 0.1, 0.3, and 0.5 g respectively. The horizontal combustion results are recorded in Figure 2b, and the counterpart results of vertical burning are given in Figure S5b. Similar to the wick case, the value and dispersion of SET significantly decrease as the sample weight increases. When using a fixed diameter diaphragm (Φ 16 mm) to adsorb samples of different masses, the more saturated samples tend to have better repeatability both horizontally and vertically. Notably, the outcomes obtained from the vertical test show lower values because the upward propagation of the flame enhances the vaporization and pyrolysis of LEs, leading to more vigorous combustion behaviors. Meanwhile, samples placed vertically are easy to distribute unevenly due to the gravity effect of droplets. It should be noted that the different heating sources will also exert a considerable influence on the outcomes. In Figure S5c, the thermocouple is used to monitor the heating temperature of both gas lighter and candle. After applying the igniter for 3 S, the detected temperatures of gas lighter and candle reach 661 and 418 °C respectively. A fast, stable, and clean fire source is more conducive to combustion investigation, while the flame provided by a candle is swaying and mixed with insufficiently oxidized wax, which will interfere with the repeatability and reliability of tests. Furthermore, the ignition method also plays an important role in the initial heating process, Figure S5d displays the effect of two igniting methods. Compared with the method of removing the fire source immediately after the flame has grown, the SET value obtained by continuously applying the fire source for three seconds is relatively low. Both ignition methods achieve good repeatability, but it is critical to maintain consistency in the ignition method.

Figure 2c offers the summary of results gained from absorbed method, in the range of 0-6 g, it is obvious that the linear relationship between SET and sample mass does not exist. On the contrary, SET shows an exponential decrease with the consistent increase of sample weight regardless of the adsorption material. A higher sample mass tends to offer a lower SET value, and when the sample mass exceeds 1 g, the impact of mass fluctuations on SET becomes

relatively insignificant. However, the stringent requirements on sample mass are unfriendly to test costs and the environment. Therefore, we list and compare three mass (0.1, 0.3, 0.5 g) groups from the absorbed method in Figure 2d. The gap between the SET values tested by the different methods is narrowed as the sample mass increases. It is worth noting that when adsorbing 0.1 g of electrolyte in the fluctuation zone, GFS obtained outcomes with a lower standard deviation (SD) of 4.6, while the SDs of IP and CW are equal to 44.0 and 55.0, respectively. Utilizing a 16 mm GFS to load 0.1 g of LE presents notable advantages over IP and CW methods, which include superb test repeatability, commercial availability of separators, and alignment with the electrolyte quality assembled in laboratories.

Figure 2. The relationship between SET_0 and sample mass tested by absorbing with (a) IP and (b) GFS, the saturated group contains GFS of different sizes, and the unsaturated group corresponds to a fixed size ($\Phi 16$ mm). (c) Summary of all data obtained by absorbing method, and (d) comparison between GFS, IP, and CW methods at several specific mass of samples: 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 g, blank LE used is 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC=1/1 (v/v).

The direct burning of LE with nonflammable containers has been exploited as the simplest way to perform the assessment, where test details are recorded in Figure S6. As detailed in Figure S7a, three types of vessels: BC, GW, and Al pans (LL, LH, SL, and SH) are chosen and used to analyze the effect of container on the burning behavior. The diameter of the generally used BC is 20 mm, with a maximum loadable weight of LEs of ~ 0.5 g, and the minimum mass

required to cover the bottom evenly is ~ 0.4 g. In **Figure 3a**, the results obtained under the two masses are closely aligned (~ 75 S g^{-1}), showcasing good repeatability in both instances. Whereas the distribution of results obtained using GW is more dispersed, especially in the low mass range in fixed diameter (Figure S7b), implying a strong reliance on exposed areas. This dependency becomes more evident when employing Al lids with varying diameters and heights. By comparing the data in Figure 3b, it is apparent that for the same mass of LE loaded, smaller exposed areas and higher height are prone to produce higher SET values. During combustion, a robust heat transfer process occurs between the system and the surrounding air, leading to the dissipation of a portion of the heat, and the rate of heat exchange is significantly influenced by the exposed surface area and the depth of the container. It is worth mentioning that a windless chamber is also necessary for conducting the experiments.

Figure 3c offers the summary of data tested by all methods above, while the results of the “Absorbed” method are severely influenced by the electrolyte sample, the results of the “Placed” method are relatively unaffected. Additionally, burning 0.5 g electrolytes with BC demonstrates comparable results to the average values achieved with SL pan in the 0.4-2 g range, ensuring reliability at lower mass levels. The generality of the method for electrolytes is illustrated in Figure 3d. Besides the EC/EMC system, the similarity and repeatability of the test results of BC and SL pan methods are also reflected in EC/DMC LEs. However, there are significant discrepancies in the results obtained from testing the EC/DEC LEs, potentially attributed to the high volatility of DEC. The trend of LE thermal stability is EC/DMC > EC/EMC > EC/DEC, which is consistent with the reciprocal order of boiling points (BPs) of linear carbonates. Notably, the freshness of the electrolyte needs to be guaranteed during the experiment, and the exposure time to air should be shortened as much as possible before the combustion test. As shown in Figure S7c, upon exposure to air and storage in the atmosphere overnight, the test results of electrolytes undergo considerable divergence. Specifically, the overall dispersion of data has increased. The EC/DMC group exhibits good stability, whereas the dispersion in the EMC and DEC groups is more pronounced, which aligns precisely with the respective volatility of the linear carbonate components. Constituent solvents with different volatilization capabilities will lead to changes in the composition of LEs, which was confirmed by the NMR track in Figure S8. The increase of relative intensity of peak *a* and peak *b, c* verifies the increase of EC/DEC ratio. Additionally, results obtained from testing non-fresh DEC electrolytes in two different containers are close, suggesting that smaller vessels (such as BC) are more indicative of the combustion conditions.

Figure 3. Results tested by (a) BC containing 0.4 and 0.5 g of LE, and (b) Al pan loading with 0.4-2 g LE. (c) Summary and comparison of SET₀ data in the sample range of 0-2 g, the LE used is 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC=1/1 (v/v). (d) SET₀ of three types of LE obtained by the direct burning method: 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DMC=1/1 (v/v); 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC=1/1 (v/v); 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DEC=1/1 (v/v).

An appropriate evaluation of flame retardancy in electrolytes is imperative to provide scientific insights for the design of novel and safer electrolytes. To thoroughly study the impact of diverse fire-safety features on the LE combustion behavior and check the feasibility of uniformized methods, we collected 15 representative commercial FRs as listed in Table 3, including phosphates, fluorinated phosphates, phosphites, phosphonates, and cyclophosphazenes, which can be generally divided into phosphate (ppa), phosphite (ppi), and phosphazene (ppz) according to the chemical structure. Meanwhile, a series of important parameters are gathered for analysis, such as melting point (MP), BP, percentage of FR elements (N, P, F), molecular mass, etc. To begin with, the fire tests of LEs modified with additives at four concentrations of 5, 10, 20, and 30% (wt) are performed by BC and GFS methods, respectively. **Figure 4a** presents the SET and SEE results from BC method (0.5 g). In comparison to SET₀ (75.6 S g⁻¹), the majority of SET values exhibit a decrease upon the introduction of additives. However, the extent of this reduction is not prominent, and an anomalous phenomenon of prolonged combustion time is observed (corresponding to a

negative SEE value), which has not been reported in previous studies. According to the different phenomena, all FRs can be generally divided into three categories: (i) significant group includes TEPI, TMPi, TPPI, TTFPI, PFPN, and FPPN, which are composed of phosphite and cyclophosphazene; (ii) moderate type consists of TEP, TMP, DMMP, TFMP, and TFP, which are phosphate-based; and (iii) prolonged class involve TOP, DPOF, CDP, and TPP, which possess benzene rings or long alkyl chains in structure. From the above classification, phosphite exhibits distinct advantages over phosphate in enhancing the fire-resistant properties of electrolytes. In parallel, Figure 4b provides the results evaluated by the GFS method. The efficacy of additives in fire suppression becomes more prominent after utilizing diaphragms as adsorption bases, particularly noteworthy when the additive amounts up to 20%, the majority of SEE cluster within the range of 90-100%. Remarkably, within the above-prolonged group, CDP and TPP demonstrate flame retardant effects, whereas TOP and DPOF exhibit a decrease in SEE with rising contents. Through the above comparative analysis, it can be inferred that the direct combustion method provides a more rigorous evaluation compared to the adsorption one. Figure S9a provides the SET and SEE classification distribution based on the results obtained from the GFS method, where the categorization of SET and SEE are distinguished by pattern shapes and colors respectively. In Figure S9b, there is no objection to the classification of the “Nonflammable” group, the main statistical dissent lies in the classification of “Flame Retarded” group and “Flammable” group. Compared with the blank LE with a SET_0 of 134.6 S g^{-1} , the SET values of 40 S g^{-1} (SEE ~70%) and 13 S g^{-1} (SEE ~90%) present diverse extents of flame retardancy, corresponding to the boundaries between flammable and flame-retardant, flame-retardant and non-flammable, respectively, instead of the fixed boundaries in SET classification. In the form of relative rate boundaries (70% and 90%), SEE can avoid the irrationality caused by the fixed boundary value (20 and 6 S g^{-1}) in the SET classification, which permits the specific boundary value converted by SET_0 for different system (represent different test methods), thereby achieving comparability and reference significance between different works.

Table 3. Structure and basic information of FRs.

NO	Chemical Name	Abbr	Structure	Types	BP ^{d)}	MP ^{e)}	FP ^{f)}	Mass	Ref
1	Triethyl phosphate	TEP		ppa ^{a)}	215	-56.4	117	182.2	[2d, 19, 29]
2	Triethyl phosphite	TEPI		ppi ^{b)}	156.6	-112	54	166.2	[2d]
3	Trimethyl phosphate	TMP		ppa	197	-46	107	140.1	[19, 29a]

4	Trimethyl phosphite	TMPi		ppi	110	-78	28	124.1	[30]
5	Trioctyl phosphate	TOP		ppa	370	-70	216	434.6	[31]
6	Dimethyl methylphosphonate	DMMP		ppa	180	-50	68.9	124.1	[32]
7	2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate	DPOF		ppa	375	-54	224	362.4	[33]
8	Cresyl diphenyl phosphate	CDP		ppa	255	-30	232	340.3	[19]
9	Triphenyl phosphate	TPP		ppa	370	49	220	326.3	[15, 34]
10	Triphenyl phosphite	TPPi		ppi	360	23	218	310.3	[35]
11	Bis(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)methylphosphonate	TFMP		ppa	184	26	80	260.1	[32b]
12	Tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)phosphate	TFP		ppa	178	-19.6	60.4	344.1	[36]
13	Tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)phosphite	TFPi		ppi	130	-28.5	113	328.1	[37]
14	Ethoxy(pentafluoro)cyclotriphosphazene	PFPN		ppz ^{e)}	125	-34	-	275.0	[21, 38]
15	Pentafluoro(phenoxy)cyclotriphosphazene	FPPN		ppz	-	-	-	323.0	[39]

a): phosphate; b): phosphite; c): phosphazene; d): boiling point; e): melting point; f): flash point

To clarify the reasons for varying behaviors of different FRs in LE, the real-time FTIR facility is employed to detect the fragments released by additives in the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) test. TMP and TFP are selected as representatives of moderately significant FRs, while TPP, DPOF, and CDP are chosen as examples of the prolonged group. As shown in Figure 4c and 4d, compared with TPP, TMP exhibits a lower temperature of decomposition and higher intensity of released fragments. The released products mainly contained phosphorus-based and carbon-based structures,^[40] including P=O (1301 cm⁻¹), P-O (846 cm⁻¹), C-O (1056 cm⁻¹), and -CH₃ (2963 and 2862 cm⁻¹). For the TFP compound, Figure S10a confirms the existence of fluorine-containing structures (-CF₃, 1182 cm⁻¹). In contrast, Figure 4e shows that

fewer phosphorus-based fragments are generated from TPP, similar to observations with CDP and DPOF (Figure S10b and S10c). Meantime, the morphology of separators after burning is recorded by SEM. After being immersed in LE, the fibrous structure on the surface remains well after combustion, which is attributed to the exceptional thermal stability of GFS (Figure S11a and S11b). Whereas the burned separator exhibits persistent areas of carbon residue with many hole structures after the addition of 20% TMP/TFP to LE (Figure S11c and S11d). When the same concentration of TPP/CDP is introduced, a denser carbon residue is observed (Figure S11e and S11f). This is ascribed to the heightened thermal stability of additives, leading to the production of limited gas phase components, with a greater retention in the condensed phase to form a protective layer.

The distinction in thermal stability among various additive types is more intuitive in the differential thermal analysis (DTA) curves. In **Figure 5a**, the peak decomposition rates of TMP, TFP, and DMMP occur at 89.4, 83.1, and 104.8 °C, respectively, while the onset temperature of degradation of TPP, DPOF, and CDP are found around 150 °C and their peak decomposition rates appear at 238.6, 243.1, and 264.8 °C, respectively. Besides, there is no residue remaining after 400 °C for all additives. To comprehend the differences in results obtained by the two methods, we initially employ thermocouples to separately monitor the temperature changes of two sites during combustion. In the BC method, the selected spots are (1) the bottom of BC and (2) the center of flame. For the GFS method, the selected points are (1) the surface of diaphragm and (2) the center of flame. As shown in Figure 5b and S12a, the LE loaded at the bottom of BC reaches a maximum temperature of 308 °C, and the flame center achieves a maximum temperature of 852 °C. On the other hand, the surface of the diaphragm attains a peak temperature of 422 °C with a maximum flame core temperature of 785 °C. It indicates that the gas-phase combustion associated with the direct combustion method is more vigorous, which allows FRs with a lower boiling/decomposition point release into the gas phase to exert the flame retardant effect. Whereas the adsorption method, represented by GFS, can concentrate more heat in the condensed phase, which facilitates the gasification and pyrolysis of more stable FRs. When the temperatures of these two points are monitored simultaneously, the results are similar (Figure S12b). Furthermore, the results of ignition using different fire sources are also compared in Figure S12c. The overall temperature of combustion using candle ignition is lower than that using a gas igniter, emphasizing the difference in the impact of different igniters. As indicated by the finite element method (FEM) simulation in Figure 5c and S13, the iron grid platform dissipates less heat than BC during the LE combustion process, validating the distinct

temperature distribution of two methods in Figure 5b and indicating a preferable choice of using GFS method.

Figure 4. Fire safety performance of modified LEs evaluated by (a) BC and (b) GFS methods. (c) The FTIR spectra of volatile products released at the maximum decomposition rate and corresponding real-time FTIR spectra of (d) TMP and (e) TPP.

Combined with the above results, the working principle of FRs is proposed and illustrated in Figure 5d. Additives with high volatility and low BPs, such as phosphite, are susceptible to vaporization upon ignition of the LEs. The pronounced release during vaporization and pyrolysis, whether as entire molecules or smaller fragments, likely plays a crucial role in the dilution effect observed with these additives. For phosphates such as TMP, it is speculated that they first vaporized and then cracked in performing their fire resistance effects. Specifically, the non-combustible gases generated during gasification can effectively dilute the concentration of vaporized LEs. With the temperature increases, FRs undergo further decomposition, and the resulting phosphorus-containing fragments can exert a quenching effect.^[34] Regards to phenyl-phosphate, such as TPP, their limited release of gas-phase products leads to a suboptimal

dilution effect during the electrolyte decomposition process.^[41] Although some phosphorus-based fragments (such as P=O, P-O) that can quench the combustion reaction are generated during the flame propagation, the combustion is difficult to suppress due to the full development of the fire, which instead results in prolonged burning time and the negative SEE values.

Figure 5. (a) DTA curves for some representative FRs: TFP, TMP, DMMP, TPP, DPOF, and CDP. (b) Temperature monitoring during the LE combustion by GFS method. (c) Temperature field of the test platform of grid and BC during burning, (d) the proposed mechanism of FRs in LEs, and feature importance of (e) SEE(class)-Ref, (f) SEE(class)-BC, and (g) SEE(class)-GFS models.

To compare the impact of various features on SEE between the Reference- and Experiment-datasets, three classification models are built with Reference-, BC-, and GFS-datasets, respectively. Starting from the FR mechanism in LEs, we specify the features with comprehensiveness and generality as described in the Experimental section. All three models

show satisfactory performance with high R^2 over 0.82 in testsets and negligible prediction errors in trainsets and below 1 in testsets. As shown in Figure 5e, “Mass” is the dominant feature with an importance of 0.521 in the Reference-model, while the most significant influencing factor in the BC- and GFS-models is the effective element content (“FR(%)” in Figure 5f and 5g), accounting for 0.270 and 0.439, respectively. This clear difference suggests that the intrinsic properties of FRs have a greater impact on the experimental group models compared to the Reference-model. Except for chemical composition, the boiling point (“BP”) of additives contributes significantly to influencing the SEE, and it occupies an importance of 0.228 in the SEE(class)-BC model, which is consistent with the above description that the vapor phase combustion of electrolytes in BC method is more vigorous (Figure S12). The ranking outcome tangentially validates our aforementioned hypothesis (Figure 5d): the pivotal aspect of flame retardancy involves disrupting the reaction chain during LE combustion, so the abundance of effective FR components in the gas phase significantly influences the self-extinguishing behavior of LEs. Besides, flash point (“FP”) has an unneglect influence on all models, which fits well with previous studies that the higher FP of FRs is prone to help inhibit the flammability of electrolytes.^[22] However, “P_Type” as the type of phosphorous in the additive molecules, is almost the least important feature in all models. Overall, the selection of FRs influences SEE results strongly, which also can be observed by the feature importance bar chart from one model using both BC- and GFS-datasets (SEE(class)-Exp model, Figure S14). The difference between reference and experimental models might be caused by the dissimilar testing methods of SET. In the SET characterization, the loading method, mass of electrolyte, combustion surface area, and ignition behavior will influence the measuring results considerably. These features are difficult to extract completely from the limited description in publications, remaining obstacles in the precise modeling, which again emphasizes the necessity of this work to establish guidelines to evaluate the self-extinguishing behavior of LE.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we proposed a novel concept of self-extinguishing efficiency (SEE) and screened a reliable test protocol to establish a comparable safety assessment for liquid electrolytes (LEs), that is burning a 16 mm diameter glassfiber separator (GFS) with the absorption of 0.1 g LE horizontally. The impact of test conditions on the assessment results was demonstrated, including ignition source, placement, ignition method, etc., and the critical effects of using a clean fire source, ensuring a wind-free chamber, and employing a fixed ignition method on experimental repeatability were highlighted. Meanwhile, 15 representative commercial flame

retardants (FRs) were assessed through the proposed SEE index, and a new flame retardant mechanism was formulated to elucidate the role of FRs in LEs, which pointed out that the vaporization and/or pyrolysis of additives preceding or synchronizing with the decomposition range of LE is conducive to flame retardancy. Furthermore, machine learning (ML) was utilized to analyze the impact of different FR features on the combustion behavior of LEs, further verifying the mechanism. This study enables a comparative analysis of the fire safety performance of LEs in Li-ion batteries (LIBs), which offers reliable support for choosing suitable electrolyte candidates in industrial applications and provides a reference for establishing standardized evaluation methods for batteries on different scales.

4. Experimental Methods

Materials: Battery grade commercial electrolytes: Lithium hexafluorophosphate solution in ethylene carbonate and diethyl carbonate, 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DEC=1/1 (v/v); Lithium hexafluorophosphate solution in ethylene carbonate and dimethyl carbonate, 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DMC=1/1 (v/v); Lithium hexafluorophosphate solution in ethylene carbonate and ethyl methyl carbonate, 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/EMC=1/1 (v/v), and Whatman® glass microfiber separators, Grade GF/A (GFS) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and stored in glove box once received. Cotton wicks (CW) of different diameters (Φ2, 4, 6, 8 mm), ceramic fiber paper biosoluble insulfrax paper (IP), battery case (BC), and glass watch (GW, Φ40, 60 mm) were purchased from markets, GFS, CW, and IP were cut in different size for purposes. To analyze the flame retardant performance of additives, 15 additives were chosen and bought. Among them, Triethyl phosphate (TEP), Trimethyl phosphate (TMP), Trimethyl phosphite (TMPi), Trioctyl phosphate (TOP), Dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP), Triphenyl phosphate (TPP), Triphenyl Phosphite (TPPi), Bis(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) methylphosphonate (TFMP), Tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)phosphate (TTFP), Ethoxy(pentafluoro)cyclotriphosphazene (PFPN), and Pentafluoro(phenoxy)cyclotriphosphazene (FPPN) were ordered from Sigma-Aldrich. Tris(4-methoxyphenyl)phosphine (TMPPi), 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate (DPOF), Cresyl Diphenyl Phosphate (CDP), Tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl) phosphite (TTFPi) were acquired from TCI Chemicals.

Characterization: Thermogravimetric analysis coupled to Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (TGA-FTIR) measurement was carried out on a TA Q50 coupled with a Thermofisher Nicolet 5700 spectrophotometer. About 10 mg of each sample was heated from room temperature to 500 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ under nitrogen. Morphological analyses were carried out by a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) instrument (Apreo 2S,

ThermoFisher with 5 or 15 kV), the samples were sputtered with gold with a spraying time of 120 seconds and 40 mA.

Fire test: The combustion experiments vary in detail for different materials. Specifically, the wick is hung on an iron stand using a clip and ignited from the bottom end; As for the separator and insulfrax paper, they are positioned horizontally on an iron grid and ignited from the bottom. For the direct combustion method using different containers, the fire source is applied vertically from the top. All the above experiments were conducted using a portable gas igniter and were completed in a windless chamber. Each experiment was repeated five times. The igniter was removed once a stable flame was formed, note that if the ignition time exceeds 5 seconds without initiating a fire, it is recorded as non-flammable. Meanwhile, it is necessary to store LE samples in sealed, light-proof bottles in the glove box to keep freshness before the experiment. When conducting combustion tests, the exposure time to air should be shortened as much as possible.

Machine learning approach: The data for building machine learning models were retrieved from the publications and measured with the lab experiments. Based on the data collected from literature and the conversion formula between SET and SEE (Equation 4), two models, SET(number)-Ref and SEE(number)-Ref, were established. Both models have a range from 0 to over or around 100, depending on the flame retardancy of additives in LEs. Due to the large numerical range of SET, the SEE values of collected data and experimental data are set as target features and divided into 3 categories (Table 2), marked with numbers 1, 2, and 3. According to their different sources, the data was divided into 3 datasets: SEE(class)-Ref, SEE(class)-BC, and SEE(class)-GFS dataset. The Reference dataset has 181 rows of data, while the latter two datasets possess data sizes of 60 and 60, respectively. Furthermore, we combined the SEE(class)-BC, and SEE(class)-GFS datasets to the SEE(class)-Exp dataset with a size of 120.

As listed in Table S2 the selected features in datasets focus on the properties of additives. For simplification, “SET0” was selected as the representative of blank electrolyte components. The additives were featured with their chemical compositions (the molar content of FR elements and molecular weight) and physical properties (the flashing, boiling, and melting points). Since the measured SET value strongly depends on the specific test method, the “Burn” feature was used to roughly distinguish the differences in characterization. Taking accessibility and generalizability into account, the selected features have covered most of the relevant aspects of flame-retardant LEs. Before modeling and optimization, the collected data was cleaned and processed by using encoders and scalers to construct input datasets with uniform distribution, proper data structure, and selected features. Additionally, the feature map was inspected to

decide which features to discard and retain as few redundant features as possible. Figure S15 depicts the heatmap of Spearman's rank correlation coefficient between two features in the datasets. The highly correlated are concentrated in the properties of FRs such as "BP", "Molar", and "FR(%)". Depending on the models to predict SEE or SET among different datasets, the selected features can vary in number and type.

The selected machine learning algorithm is a widely used tree ensemble for supervised learning. This Random Forest (RF) method combines plenty of randomly grown decision trees to lower the variance or bias, reducing the risk of overfitting. While modeling, 85% of the input dataset was considered as a trainset to train the models, and the remaining 15% as testset to evaluate the predictive accuracy instantly. The split was done randomly and marked as the random state. In the RF algorithm, hyperparameters (HP) are used to control the number, shape, and size of decision trees. Optimization of these HPs is conducted with trainsets, and the trained models are then used to make predictions with testsets to evaluate their predictive accuracy. The optimized HPs of all RF models are explained and listed in Table S3 and S4, together with the values of model indices in Table S5. Except for the R2 scores, mean errors of the predictions compared to the true values were collected to evaluate the predictive performance of ML models. The calculation of feature importance is realized with the built-in function, which represents the percentage impact of an individual feature on the target property. The sum of all features' importance counts as 1. The higher the feature importance is, the more significant the feature is to the change of target property. Ranking the features by their importance provides a way to filter the necessary features to achieve better predictive performance with simpler models and analyze the underlying mechanisms in the right direction.

Heat transfer Finite Element Method (FEM) model: A three-dimensional thermal conduction model was established based on the COMSOL Multiphysics 6.1. A membrane with a diameter of 16 mm and a thickness of 0.1 mm was set to have a huge thermal capacity to simulate its state with flame (Table S6). The initial temperatures of 581.15 K and 695.15 K of the flame for the BC and the grid were set based on the thermocouple test, respectively. The battery case and the grid were constructed from stainless steel and iron, respectively, with an initial temperature set to match the environment at 298.15 K. The durations for the entire thermal conduction process were set at 10 S for the grid and 40 S for the button battery case, in accordance with the measurements. The governing equation of energy conservation equation and thermal conduction are expressed as follows:

$$\rho C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T \right) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = Q \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{q} = -k\nabla T \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the density (kg m^{-3}), C_p is the specific heat capacity at constant stress ($\text{J (kg}\cdot\text{K)}^{-1}$), T is the absolute temperature (K), \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector of translational motion (m s^{-1}), \mathbf{q} is the heat flux by conduction (W m^{-2}), Q contains additional heat sources (W m^{-3}), and k is the thermal conductivity ($\text{W (m}\cdot\text{K)}^{-1}$).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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